

Silicon nanowire aqueous dispersions for processing into macroscopic network materials[†]

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Nanowires and other high aspect ratio nanoparticles are building blocks to form network materials in formats such as films, sheets, fibres and electrodes that thus bridge the nano and macro scales. The assembly of nanowire network materials is enabled by a new floating catalyst chemical vapour deposition synthesis method that produces crystalline silicon nanowires (SiNW) on a scale of grams per day. Here, we produce SiNW dispersions in water by sonication through steric and electrostatic stabilisation of the negatively charged particles in basic pH or with cationic surfactants. Negative charge arises from the 1.3 nm-thin native oxide layer. Some permanent aggregates are found as a consequence of cross-links between the thin oxide at the surface of adjacent SiNWs. Removing them by centrifugation yields SiNW dispersions of 52 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. Processing into macroscopic materials is demonstrated as transparent films and as freestanding sheets. In the sheets the SiNWs are predominantly aligned parallel to the sheet thickness, as a paper-like SiNW solid with tensile strength above 10 MPa, modulus above 1 GPa and toughness of 0.5 J g⁻¹.

Nanowires (NW) are rod-like inorganic nanomaterials which generate great interest due to their shape and intrinsic physico-chemical properties¹, and their applications in catalysis², energy storage^{3–5} and optoelectronics^{6,7}. For these and other applications, it is essential to have methods that enable controlled assembly of a large number of nanowires into aggregated networks to make macroscopic materials in the form of electrodes, fibres, membranes, etc.

Wet-processing has proved a successful route to assemble nanobuilding blocks into macromaterials with versatile format ranging from dense fibres⁸, to polymer nanocomposites⁹ to transparent films¹⁰. Furthermore, 1D nanomaterials stabilized in liquid matrix are an ideal system to make calamitic liquid crystals^{11,12}, potentially enabling formation of highly ordered nanowire domains to produce macroscopic ensembles with long-range order.

This work introduces a method to stabilise aqueous dispersions of silicon nanowires (SiNW) and use them to form self-standing macroscopic networks. The SiNW are synthesised by floating catalyst chemical vapour deposition (FCCVD), a new method that enables continuous synthesis of crystalline nanowires of high aspect ratio on the scale of grams per day¹³. The synthesis process is the same as our previous work¹⁴ (see at the Supplementary Information 1 (SI 1)). The starting material is in the form of a powder made of agglomerated nanowires, as depicted in Fig. 1

(a). The nanowires are monocrystalline with a mean diameter of 23 nm and length of 1.5 μm . They have a thin native oxide layer of approximately 1.3 nm formed upon exposure to air, as illustrated in Fig. 1 (b). This oxide layer is revealed by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) of the powder. The vibrational modes related to oxide species of silicon and the absence of the Si–H_x band¹⁵ are shown in the inset of Fig. 1 (c). Additionally, Raman spectroscopy (Fig. 1 (d)) revealed the high purity and crystallinity of the SiNWs, approximately 97.8%, by comparing the amorphous silicon (490 cm⁻¹ band) and the crystalline silicon (515 cm⁻¹ band)¹⁶.

Fig. 1 Characterization of the SiNWs powder: (a) SiNW powder as collected from the FCCVD synthesis reactor, (b) TEM image of SiNW and the native oxide layer (scale bar: 10 nm), (c) FTIR analysis of the powder, (d) Raman spectra of the SiNW.

The thin oxide layer strongly influences colloidal properties and facilitates dispersion in aqueous media. Attempts to disperse SiNW through tip sonication in non-polar solvents such as tetrahydrofuran, dichloromethane, or toluene (bottom image of Fig. 2 (a)) were unsuccessful. Previous studies^{17,18} have shown that chemical functionalization and/or the absence of an oxide layer on the surface of the silicon colloidal nanoparticles is required. Micrographs revealed large aggregates visible to the naked eye. Conversely, tip sonication for 1 hour in water and ethanol readily enabled the disaggregation of SiNW powder, re-

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sulting in homogeneous suspensions. This underscores the clear impact of the oxide layer in suspending colloidal silicon in deionized water¹⁹ or through chemical functionalization²⁰. Fig. 2 (b) illustrates the evolution of the SiNW zeta potential in aqueous solution at different pH levels. The isoelectric point is at pH 3, indicating that the nanowires are negatively charged. Furthermore, decreasing the pH reveals the effects of electrostatic charges. At pH 7, a turbid suspension forms, but below this pH, aggregates are visible by naked eye (see SI 2).

This zeta potential profile closely resembles that found in colloidal silica in water²¹, which has an isoelectric point around pH 3-4. Thus, it is evident that the negative charge on the nanowires is due to the native oxide, and dispersion methods developed for silica nanoparticles can be applied to SiNWs. This includes, for example, the use of cationic surfactants in silica nanoparticle suspensions in water, such as cetrimonium bromide (CTAB). Indeed, adding as little as 0.2 wt.% CTAB at pH 7 changes the zeta potential from -30 mV to +40 mV, resulting in a stable dispersion. The negative charges of the SiNW are counteracted by the cationic groups of CTAB and the Van der Waals forces by micelle formation.

The aqueous dispersions of SiNWs were found to be stable but optically cloudy (inset top image of Fig. 2 (a), even after reducing the concentration significantly to 1 mg mL⁻¹ and below. This indicates the presence of aggregates in the dispersion, which are themselves stabilized by electrostatic charges and formation of micelles. SI 3 presents the evolution of the suspension, comparing ethanol and aqueous suspensions with CTAB and basic pH after 3 weeks. Although sediments are observed at the bottom of the aqueous suspensions, there is a clear difference compared to polar solvents such as ethanol. However, after centrifugation at 10,000 g for 30 minutes, two phases are formed (see SI 4): a clear stable dispersion and a sediment of aggregates. Thus, the initial dispersion is in fact a mixture of individualised SiNWs and aggregates of SiNWs. These aggregates were persistently observed, even after varying the concentration of surfactant, time or sonication energy. The sedimented aggregates were found to have a log-normal size distribution with an apparent average diameter of 2.08 $\mu\text{m} \pm 0.02$ obtained from optical micrographs. We hypothesise that the aggregates have SiNWs which are cross-linked through the native oxide layer formed upon exposure of the material to ambient conditions, similar to how primary silica nanoparticles are found covalently bonded in aggregates²². A critical size for sedimentation of an aggregate can be estimated by comparing the gravitational force and that associated to Brownian motion. We treat the aggregates as fractal-like structures. Assuming a quasi-spherical aggregate of diameter d_{agg} , the diffusion force is simply $k_B T / d_{agg}$. The gravitational force on an aggregate of mass M_{agg} is:

$$F_g = M_{agg} g = V_{NW} N_{NW} \rho_{Si} g$$

Where V_{NW} is the mean volume of a nanowire, N_{NW} the number of nanowires in an aggregate and ρ_{Si} the density of silicon. In a study of agglomerates of SiNWs collected from the gas phase analysed by electron microscopy, it was found that the radius of gyration (R_g) of agglomerates/aggregates is related to the number of nanowires by the following expression²³

$$N = k_0 \left(\frac{R_g}{b} \right)^{D_f}$$

Where b is a nanowire size parameter, $D_f = 1.8$ the agglomerate fractal dimension and $k_0 = 2$ is a constant pre-factor. And from experimental observation, the nanowire agglomerate diameter and radius of gyration follow

$$d_{agg} \approx 13.5 R_g$$

Using these expressions we find that fractal-like aggregates would settle for sizes around 6 μm , which is indeed similar to the average aggregate size found in the optical micrographs (see Fig. S5 in SI).

After centrifugation at 10,000 g for 30 minutes the supernatant can be extracted for further analysis and processing of the dispersion of individualised SiNWs. This speed ensures the removal of aggregates from the suspension. A typical photograph of the supernatant can be seen in the inset of Fig. 2 (d), demonstrating formation of a clear dispersion.

To evaluate the concentration of SiNW in the supernatant, UV-vis spectroscopy was used. The cloudy SiNW suspension was di-

Fig. 2 Preparation of stable suspensions of SiNWs: (a) optical micrographs of the 0.05 wt.% SiNW suspensions in deionized water and CTAB (top) and toluene (bottom), (b) zeta-potential of 0.05 wt.% SiNWs in water versus pH, (c) UV absorption spectra of SiNW suspensions with different concentrations, (d) SEM image of individualized SiNW after centrifugation. The inset is a photograph of the resulting clear dispersion (scale bar: 5 μm). Comparison of (e) length and (f) diameter distributions of the individualised material and the original SiNWs showing that the dispersion process does not shorten the nanowires.

Fig. 3 Wet-processed macroscopic networks of SiNWs by vacuum filtration. (a) SiNW transparent film prepared by dissolving the filter membrane and wet-transfer to FTO (scale bar: 1 cm), (b) SEM micrograph of the top view of the SiNW film (scale bar: 5 μm) and (c) the comparison of the Raman spectra of powder and film. (d) Free-standing sheet of SiNW after dissolving the supporting membrane (scale bar: 3 mm), (e) stress-strain curves of cut samples from the sheet of $2 \times 1 \text{ mm}^2$ and $9.5 \mu\text{m}$ (the inset is 2D SAXS pattern obtained with the beam through the thickness of the SiNW sheet, showing preferential alignment) and (f) fracture energy versus the solid fraction (network density/crystal density) of this macromaterial compared with other self-assembled nanomaterials (adapted from Schäuferle *et al.*¹⁴).

luted with deionized water while keeping the CTAB concentration constant. In the Fig. 2(c), a broad band at 386 nm was observed, with its intensity showing a linear dependence on the SiNW concentration. Accordingly, the concentration of the supernatant was found to be $52 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. Casting a small volume of the dispersion on a substrate enables direct observation and dimensional analysis from scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images (Fig. 2(d). The length and diameter distributions of the SiNW population are presented in Fig. 2 (e) and (f) and compared to the original material sampled directly from the gas phase²³. The results show that both distributions are log-normal, reminiscent of the log-normal catalyst size distribution used in FCCVD¹³. There are no appreciable differences in SiNW length, which is $1.47 \pm 0.84 \mu\text{m}$ in the dispersed SiNWs and $1.44 \pm 0.38 \mu\text{m}$ in the original material, suggesting that the sonication process does not shorten the nanowires, which can be the case during dispersion of other nanoparticles. Furthermore, a comparison of Raman spectra (Fig. 3 (c)) gives no indication of the dispersion method introducing defects of compositional

changes. There is a small difference in mean diameter, which is $23.25 \pm 5.92 \text{ nm}$ for the supernatant material and $21.35 \pm 0.20 \text{ nm}$ for the original SiNWs. This may be from limitations of the image analysis method used here, which relies on identification of each NW for analysis by the researcher, rather than an unbiased automated system. Taking the mean values of the distributions, the aspect ratio is 63.2 for the individualised nanowires and 67.4 for the as-made nanomaterial.

Having a stable dispersion of individualised nanowires unlocks a plethora of wet-processing methods to make devices and to form macroscopic materials. Here we use vacuum filtration²⁴ to demonstrate the fabrication of SiNWs networks. To achieve this, 10 mL of the supernatant solution is filtered through a polycarbonate track etched membrane (25 mm diameter and $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ pore size), followed by washing with deionized water to remove the surfactant and then drying in an oven at $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Subsequently, the filter was dissolved in a bath of N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) to form a suspended SiNW network. Then, it was submerged using a mesh into an acetone bath to remove the NMP and dry it under room temperature conditions. A thin network can be easily transferred onto a fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO) substrate to form a transparent film (Fig. 3 (a) and (b)), with the common format of a photoelectrode.

Alternatively, a thicker network can directly form a freestanding structure without the need for a supporting substrate. To increase thickness, the centrifugation duration can be reduced to 10 minutes (e.g., at 10,000 g), resulting in a clear dispersion and concentration of 0.1 mg mL^{-1} . Vacuum filtration of the supernatant suspension produces a thick network that now forms a freestanding sheet by simply removing the membrane in the NMP bath, washing with acetone, and drying under air. The resulting material is a paper-like flexible network of nanowires with an average thickness of $9.3 \pm 0.9 \mu\text{m}$ (see SI 6), as shown in the photograph in Fig. 3 (d). Its apparent density, calculated by measuring the volume and weight after removing the solvents at $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 hours under N_2 atmosphere, is 0.15 g cm^{-3} .

Edge-on small-angle X-ray (SAXS) measurements show preferential alignment of SiNWs through the thickness, evident from the elongated shape of the pattern (Fig. 3 (e) inset) and the Lorentzian line shape of the azimuthal profile, with a full width at half maximum (FWHM) of $33.2^\circ \pm 0.3^\circ$ (see SI 7). In materials comprised of networks of high aspect ratio elements, bulk properties are dominated by the alignment of the building blocks¹³. Higher alignment increases packing of nanowires, significantly improving bulk properties by increasing stress and charge transfer between neighbouring nanowires. Effectively, the results in this work demonstrate stable dispersions of individualised nanowires enabling processing into macroscopic network materials with control to impart alignment during assembly and thus access to superior bulk properties. This is highlighted by the mechanical properties shown in Fig. 3 (e). The sheet exhibits behavior similar to that of CNT sheets. The profile of the stress-strain curves demonstrates an elasto-plastic response, which combines the deformation of SiNWs with the slippage of the nanowires in the network, resulting in a Young's modulus of $1.0 \pm 0.2 \text{ GPa}$ and an ultimate tensile strength of $11.5 \pm 1.0 \text{ MPa}$. Additionally, this cooperative behavior of the network provides an

average toughness (i.e. fracture energy) of $0.5 \pm 0.1 \text{ J g}^{-1}$. This high toughness enables handling of the SiNW network as a macroscopic material, for example in the preparation of SiNW anodes for lithium ion batteries, one of their most promising applications. Fig. 3 (f) compares the fracture energy of different porous materials normalized by their solid fraction (network density/crystal density), showing that our work significantly exceeds the performance of various foams and is comparable to that of CNTs.

Conclusions

For most envisaged application, exploiting the outstanding properties of nanowires requires assembling a large number of them into macroscopic networks. By producing stable dispersions of SiNWs we unlock a plethora of wet-processing methods. SiNWs are found to be negatively charged due to the thin native oxide layer formed upon exposure to ambient conditions after synthesis in an inert atmosphere. As a consequence, in such format they are not dispersible in non-polar solvents but can form stable aqueous dispersions above pH 7, with an isoelectric point at acidic pH, similar to silica nanoparticles. With a conventional cationic surfactant stable dispersions of individualized SiNWs at a concentration of $52 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ are produced. After removing micron-sized agglomerates of SiNW through centrifugation clear dispersions of individualised SiNWs are formed without any degradation or shortening of the nanowires. These individualized SiNW suspensions may find use in electronics²⁰ and biomedical applications²⁵. Vacuum filtration of dispersion produces a freestanding paper-like material consisting solely of SiNWs. They are randomly oriented in the plane but aligned in the through-thickness direction, demonstrating control during assembly of SiNW into macromaterials. SiNW sheets are suitable as electrodes in Li-ion batteries³, in photocatalytic hydrogen production²⁶, for high temperature energy scavenging applications²⁷, in sensing²⁸, and other applications²⁹.

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Data Availability Statement

Supporting data included as Supplementary Information.

Conflicts of interest

J.J.V. has a financial interest in Floatech, which commercializes SiNWs.

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